

Four-dimensional filtering of InSAR persistent scatterers elucidates subsidence induced by tunnel excavation in the Sri Lankan highlands

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Abstract. During construction of the Uma Oya Multipurpose Development Project, excavation of a headrace tunnel through highly tectonized metamorphic rock was slowed by repeated major water ingress events. In total, these events resulted in an estimated aquifer depletion of over 9 million m³, causing widespread surface subsidence. Persistent scatterer (PS) time series analysis of interferometric synthetic aperture radar (InSAR) scenes acquired by Sentinel-1 between July 28, 2016, and January 7, 2018, has revealed an ~15 km² area of subsidence near reported water ingress locations, with a maximum line-of-sight subsidence value of 4.3 cm. A four-dimensional (4-D) filtering method based on averaging spatial and temporal pixel neighbors was applied to the unwrapped PS pixels, significantly reducing noise from sources that appear randomly in spatial and temporal domains and increasing the ability to accurately identify the onset of subsidence and track surface volume loss over time. A maximum average subsidence rate of 0.15 mm/day coincides with maximum tunnel discharge measurements, indicating that rock mass consolidation occurred as a result of rapid pore-pressure drawdown within an interconnected discontinuity network and led to fracture closure. The observed subsidence is punctuated by localized maxima and extends in a northwest–southeast orientation, suggesting that the extent of subsidence is governed by previously mapped structural trends of similar orientations. These results highlight the value of the 4-D filtering approach in processing InSAR PS data to help determine the magnitude and extent of surface subsidence. © 2019 Society of Photo-Optical

Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) | DOI: 10.1117/1.JRS.13.034508

Keywords: InSAR; persistent scatterers; deformation; settlement; tunneling; Uma Oya; aquifer depletion.

Paper 181007 received Jan. 3, 2019; accepted for publication Jul. 9, 2019; published online Jul. 27, 2019.

1 Introduction

The Uma Oya Multipurpose Development Project (UOMDP) began construction in 2014 within the Badulla district of Sri Lanka and is designed to provide power and irrigation water to local communities. The project consists of two reservoirs connected by a link tunnel, a headrace tunnel, a tailrace tunnel, and a vertical pressure shaft connected to a powerhouse. The 15.3-km long headrace tunnel redirects reservoir water to a 628-m vertical pressure shaft above a hydropower station (Fig. 1).^{1,2} The headrace and tailrace tunnels were excavated via a 4.3-m diameter double shield tunnel boring machine. Excavation of the headrace tunnel at depth through heavily fractured, granulite facies metamorphic rock of the Sri Lankan highland complex has led to recurring water ingress during the tunnel boring phase of the UOMDP.^{1,3} The largest such event took place between September 2016 and December 2017. During this time, peak water ingress discharge reached nearly 1400 l/s. As a consequence, surface water resources were heavily impacted as hundreds of wells and several streams ran dry.^{1,4} Additionally, many buildings were reportedly damaged due to suspected surface subsidence related to aquifer depletion.⁵

Large tunneling-induced surface settlements are often observed above deep (>200 m) tunnels excavated through fractured crystalline rock.^{6–10} Interferometric synthetic aperture radar

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Fig. 1 Map showing the alignment of the headrace tunnel as well as the locations of the constructed dams, pressure shaft, major water ingress events, and extent of measured subsidence underlain by a DEM.

(InSAR) is an ideal geodetic tool for detecting, measuring, and monitoring such surface deformation. Satellite data availability has improved dramatically in recent years, which makes InSAR an increasingly viable option for monitoring surface displacements induced by tunneling activities.^{6,7,11–14} To measure surface deformation associated with the UOMDP, an ascending dataset of 33 C-band ($\lambda \sim 5.6$ cm) SAR images acquired by the Sentinel-1 constellation was processed using persistent scatterer (PS) time series analysis to determine the extent and magnitude of subsidence surrounding the tunnel axis. To further reduce noise present within the dataset, we apply a four-dimensional (4-D) filtering algorithm, similar to that proposed by Kromer et al.¹⁵ for point-cloud-based slope monitoring to the PS time series. This method takes advantage of the high spatial and temporal resolution of the dataset relative to the spatial extent and temporal rate of deformation. After developing a similar method for use with InSAR data specifically, we apply it to our dataset to reduce noise and more accurately map the extent and timing of measured subsidence. The application of the 4-D noise reduction algorithm shows the ability to reduce temporally uncorrelated noise within the time series, allowing for more precise identification of the onset, duration, and magnitude of observed surface settlement.

2 Methods

2.1 Persistent Scatterer Interferometry

We used repeat pass differential InSAR^{16,17} to process 33 ascending SAR scenes acquired between July 2016 and January 2018 by the Sentinel-1 A&B satellites. The GAMMA software¹⁸ was used to create a series of single master interferograms (Fig. 2) from dual vertically (VV) polarized single-look complexes, with topographic phase contribution removed via NASA's

Fig. 2 Baseline plot of single master interferograms used for StaMPS time series processing.

Shuttle Radar Topography Mission 30-m resolution digital elevation model (DEM). The perpendicular baseline was controlled within 122 m. The master scene was acquired on June 5, 2017, and the maximum temporal baseline is 312 days. After interferogram formation, all data were entered into the MATLAB-based Stanford method for persistent scatterers (StaMPS) software package.^{19,20} PSs, defined as pixels that provide stable radar reflections back to the satellite over a time period of interest, were then selected. Unlike amplitude-based PS algorithms, StaMPS identifies potential PS through an iterative procedure that estimates phase stability for all pixels in a scene. This is particularly advantageous when applied to natural terrains with rough surfaces that produce low-amplitude reflections like the highly vegetated Sri Lankan highlands.

After input of the single master interferograms, StaMPS identifies a collection of initial PS candidates based on amplitude dispersion values with a chosen threshold of 0.4.^{19,21} Once PS pixel candidates are selected, DEM error is calculated using the relationship between phase and perpendicular baseline. Calculated DEM error is then subtracted by

$$\Phi_i - \Phi_e = \Phi_{\text{def}} + \Phi_\alpha + \Phi'_e + n \quad (1)$$

where Φ_i is the initial phase, Φ_e is the DEM error, Φ_{def} is the phase change due to surface deformation, Φ_α is the atmospheric phase contribution, Φ'_e is the residual DEM error (ideally near zero), and n is a random noise component associated with all other sources of error. Since any pixel with random phase has a finite probability of being selected as a PS candidate, final PS pixels are selected by comparing the probability density function of phase stability values from the PS candidate population with that of a population of pixels with random phase. A threshold phase stability value is then selected to maximize the number of true PS pixels while keeping the proportion of potentially random pixels below a specific value. For our dataset, an average random pixel density threshold of 20 pixels/km² was used. This process iterates until convergence on a statistically robust set of pixels, reducing the impact of temporal decorrelation and improving the signal-to-noise ratio for each interferogram. Data are then unwrapped within StaMPS using a stepwise 3-D unwrapping algorithm.²²

It is often highly difficult to separate atmospheric phase contributions from the desired deformation signal.^{23,24} Tropospheric effects are caused by variations in pressure, temperature, and relative humidity in the lower troposphere and are capable of obscuring signals of interest,^{25,26} especially in tropical areas that experience large fluctuations in tropospheric water vapor density,²⁷ such as Sri Lanka. Because each interferogram contains the same master scene, the atmospheric phase contribution from that scene is present in all interferograms and therefore correlates

in space and time. The atmospheric phase delay from the master scene is estimated and removed in StaMPS using a low-pass filter in the temporal domain. Atmospheric contributions from slave scenes, however, are more difficult to estimate because they do not correlate in time.

2.2 4-D Filtering

After PS processing, significant noise still existed within the data. Random noise can be reduced or filtered through averaging, which is especially useful for datasets with low signal-to-noise ratios. To further reduce these error sources, we have modified a 4-D filtering algorithm originally designed for use with terrestrial laser scanner data for rock slope monitoring described by Kromer et al.¹⁵ Since this method employs filters in both temporal and spatial domains, we consider any source of noise that does not correlate in both space and time to be random noise. Specifically, we attempt to reduce noise from sources including temporally uncorrelated atmosphere, residual DEM error, noise from any false-positive PS selections, and any errors introduced during phase unwrapping.

For a series of random measurements within an unknown population, regardless of the distribution in which they are sampled, sample means always converge to a Gaussian distribution. The estimation of the population mean occurs by averaging sample means. For data given in a time-series format such as InSAR PSs, each pixel possesses neighbors in both the spatial and temporal domains. Spatial averaging tends to smooth any signal, however, greater averaging in the spatial domain can be advantageous when the spatial extent of deformation is much larger than the neighborhood radius used for averaging. Similarly, averaging along the temporal domain can be applied as long as the temporal averaging window is much smaller than the expected temporal rate of change.¹⁵ In theory, averaging both spatial and temporal neighbors, as opposed to only using one or the other, has a multiplicative effect in reducing the standard error.¹⁵ This error reduction increases the potential to elucidate signal changes from data with higher levels of random noise.

We used this information to develop a 4-D noise reduction filter and applied it to a time series of PS pixels identified by StaMPS within our study area. Before applying the filter, pixels were masked if their deformation value was zero or greater, indicating no deformation or uplift, during a selected reference scene. This was done to remove stable pixels along the boundary of the subsidence signal of interest. For each remaining pixel, a given input radius defined the spatial neighborhood, while the temporal neighborhood used the same pixel location but from equal time intervals before and after the filtered scene. In total, eight equal interval radii and temporal windows were used, ranging from 0 to 210 m and 0 to 84 days, respectively. Twelve-day intervals were selected based on the repeat time of the Sentinel-1 constellation. Since the degree of surface deformation changes slowly over time, the filter ensures that an equal number of temporal neighbors is used before and after the reference scene. This means no temporal averaging occurs in the first or last scene of the time series because they are missing temporal neighbors in one direction. Therefore, scenes closer to the center of the time series have access to more temporal neighbors than those closer to the beginning or end. The procedure outputs up to 64 different combinations of spatial and temporal filtering for each of the 33 scenes in the PS time series. It is important to note that pixel values are changed based on spatial and temporal averaging, but the positioning of the PS points remains constant, unlike the case in a smoothing polygonal mesh or other filtering methods.¹⁵

Given that up to 64 filtering combinations are available for each scene, it is important to identify the optimum combination of spatial and temporal neighbors for a given scene. The appropriate number of time steps and spatial neighbors will depend on the signal being studied, specifically its spatial extent and temporal rate of change. A high degree of temporal filtering is not advised for studying processes with high temporal variability such as volcanic or earthquake deformation, or in cases where the temporal resolution of the data is limited.

Every combination results in various advantages and disadvantages depending on the amount of noise present in each scene. Combining a high degree of spatial averaging and a low number of temporal neighbors imposes a degree of smoothing, which can allow noisier pixels to propagate within a scene and reduce the ability to resolve the true signal (Fig. 3). The ideal degree of filtering is identified separately for each scene as the case that minimizes the variance of pixel

Fig. 3 Combinations of spatial and temporal filtering for an interferogram with a significant degree of noise. The selected filter combination is represented by the scene highlighted in the red box.

values in time and space. For each pixel, a spatial neighborhood is established and the variance of all pixels within it is calculated. The spatial variance for each pixel within a scene is then averaged, providing a single variance value. Temporal variance is then calculated for each pixel based on the value of the pixel in the reference scene, as well as the scenes used for temporal filtering. Temporal variances are then averaged into a single value for each scene and then averaged again with the spatial variance value. The filtering combination that produces the least overall average variance is then selected for each scene in the time series.

2.3 Volume Estimation

To better understand the relationship between surface deformation and groundwater depletion, total volume estimates were calculated for comparison. After selection of the final time series, each scene was linearly interpolated to form a complete surface across the subsiding region. These interpolated surfaces were used to calculate total volume losses due to settlement. Groundwater volume loss was then estimated by compiling reported tunnel discharges ($n = 8$ measurements) from various Sri Lankan newspaper articles and official government reports and then using a stepwise function to determine a minimum estimate of water volume.

3 Results

3.1 StaMPS Output and Optimal 4-D Filtering

After StaMPS processing and masking with a selected reference scene of November 8, 2016, 3558 PS pixels were selected within our area of interest. It is immediately clear that several scenes contain nonpermanent deformation over short time periods (Fig. 4), most notably

Fig. 4 StaMPS time series output within the study area.

between April 6 and May 12, 2017. This is unexpected given that subsurface fluid extraction is usually followed by continuous surface subsidence over short time periods^{6,7,14,28,29} and indicates that these scenes contain greater levels of noise. These short-term increases in noise are likely due to atmosphere present at the time of the slave acquisition.

The 4-D filtering method applied to the StaMPS output is designed to reduce noise in the time series by combining spatial and temporal neighbors. The optimum combination of neighbors for each scene was selected based on minimizing overall spatiotemporal variance of the data (Fig. 5). For all scenes, variance decreased with increasing temporal filtering, however, diminishing improvements were observed with each step up in window size (Fig. 5). The optimum degree

Fig. 5 Average variance of all 4-D filtering combinations for each interferogram.

Table 1 Applied spatial and temporal filter sizes.

Acquisition date	Spatial filter radius (m)	Number of temporal neighbors
July 28, 2016	30	0
October 8, 2016	150	0
November 1, 2016	120	2
November 25, 2016	120	4
December 19, 2016	120	6
January 12, 2017	120	6
February 5, 2017	120	6
February 17, 2017	120	8
March 1, 2017	120	8
March 13, 2017	120	10
March 25, 2017	90	10
April 6, 2017	90	10
April 18, 2017	90	10
April 30, 2017	120	10
May 12, 2017	30	10
May 24, 2017	120	10
June 29, 2017	180	10
July 11, 2017	60	10
July 23, 2017	120	10
August 4, 2017	120	10
August 16, 2017	90	10
August 28, 2017	120	10
September 9, 2017	150	12
September 21, 2017	210	14
October 3, 2017	150	14
October 15, 2017	60	14
October 27, 2017	150	12
November 8, 2017	210	10
November 20, 2017	90	8
December 2, 2017	210	6
December 14, 2017	210	4
December 26, 2017	180	2
January 7, 2018	210	0

of spatial filtering was found to be more variable. Scenes containing more noise tended to undergo less spatial filtering, while relatively noise-free scenes often incorporated greater spatial filter radii. The degree of spatial and temporal filtering for each acquisition is shown in Table 1.

Fig. 6 Final time series after implementation of 4-D filtering.

3.2 Observed Deformation

PS processing combined with 4-D filtering elucidates a pattern of increasing subsidence over the time period of interest (Fig. 6). Localized line-of-sight (LOS) subsidence is first observed on November 1, 2016, and subsequently expands into a well-defined pseudoelliptical area spanning $\sim 15 \text{ km}^2$. The magnitude and gradient of LOS subsidence both increase toward the center of the affected area, which forms a settlement trough aligned NNW–SSE (Fig. 7). From November 1, 2016, to November 20, 2017, a span of 384 days, a maximum total LOS subsidence of 4.3 cm was measured resulting in an average settlement of $\sim 0.1 \text{ mm/day}$. Subsidence rates vary slightly over time and are seen to have been increasing most rapidly between April 16 and August 4, 2017, when the average reached $\sim 0.15 \text{ mm/day}$ (Fig. 8).

Initial ingress began at some point after August 4, 2016, near chainage marker 8 + 840,⁴ with sustained discharges greater than 400 l/s.^{4,30} Inflows increased greatly on April 17, 2017, reaching at least 1200 l/s⁵ with some outlets reporting values as high as 1460 l/s.³¹ To determine a minimum estimate of the total groundwater volume loss over the time period of interest, we estimated discharge values using a stepwise function (Table 2). Since no timing constraints were available for peak discharge, the 1070 l/s value reported on June 21, 2017, was used for the maximum discharge. Additionally, a baseflow (i.e., corresponding to zero-subsidence) discharge of 300 l/s is assumed. Integration of the estimated hydrograph above this point results in a total minimum aquifer volume loss of 9.2 million m^3 .

4 Discussion

4.1 Consolidation Mechanism and Timing

Bedrock consolidation processes resulting from excavation-induced groundwater drainage have a history of causing surface settlements.^{6,7–10,32} In fractured crystalline rock, two hydro-mechanically coupled mechanisms are thought to induce surface settlement during drainage events. On shorter timescales, interconnected fracture networks form pathways that allow for rapid water drainage through the rock, which, in turn, reduces internal pore pressures leading to the closure of fractures. The other potential contribution involves the reduction of pore pressure within mesoscale fractures of primarily intact rock blocks, a much slower process expected to take place over several years.^{8,9}

A lag time between the occurrence of tunnel inflows and the onset of surface subsidence can indicate the primary consolidation mechanism. Best estimates currently available for

Fig. 7 Deformation spanning July 28, 2016, to November 20, 2017, highlighting the location of maximum measured LOS subsidence and the tunnel alignment. The profile line shown was used to interpolate displacements shown in Fig. 8.

diffusion times between tunnel and ground surface range between 8 h to 165 days but are dependent upon the geometry of the fracture network, as well as tunnel depth relative to the water table.³ Our time series results fall within this range, with surface settlement having begun between October 8 and November 1, 2016, approximately 65 to 89 days after the initial onset of inflows after August 4, 2016. The coincident timing between increased tunnel discharge and increased subsidence rates during the April 2017 major ingress event (Fig. 9) indicates a direct relationship between aquifer depletion and surface deformation. Additionally, over a centimeter of rebound is measured between November 20, 2017, and January 7, 2018, a time period that coincides with a rapid reduction in tunnel discharge as it returned to baseflow levels. Temporally coincident rapid changes in both discharge and subsidence rates, combined with the fact that subsidence is only observed over a 384-day period, indicate that consolidation processes, in this case, are dominated by the closure of larger faults and fractures as opposed to long-term pore pressure reduction within intact rock blocks.

Fig. 8 Interpolated profile displacements over time.

Table 2 Discharge values reported by the Sri Lankan government and various media outlets.

Date	Reported discharge (l/s)	Source
December 31, 2016	~400	Ismail, 2017
April 17, 2017	1200	Ministry of Mahaweli Development and Environment, 2017
June 21, 2017	1070	Indrajith, 2017; Mudalige, 2017; Wickramasinghe, 2017
June 25, 2017	976	De Silva, 2017
July 2, 2017	850	“Project company promises new houses,” 2017
October 22, 2017	583	“Decrease in water leakage,” 2017; “Investigations underway into Uma Oya Project leakage,” 2017; Silva, 2017
October 23, 2017	400	“Uma Oya seepage,” 2017
December 17, 2017	200	Ministry of Mahaweli Development and Environment, 2017; Maloney, 2017

4.2 Controls on Extent and Magnitude of Subsidence

Localized maxima are found near the center of the subsiding region and are elongated in an NNW–SSE orientation similar to the long axis of the observed subsidence bowl. This trend does not directly follow the tunnel alignment, and maximum subsidence is found over 1 km away from the location, where the greatest inflow rates were measured, indicating that the location of tunnel excavation itself has little influence over the potential maximum extent of surface subsidence during large drainage events.

In hard rock environments, groundwater flow at depth is controlled by the presence of conductive fractures.³³ Previous studies have shown that tunnel inflow rates are controlled by the degree of bedrock fracturing, as opposed to the surrounding lithology or tunnel depth, especially for tunnels excavated at depths greater than 200 m.³³ This seems intuitive, as the greater the degree and persistence of fracturing, the more likely a fracture network will intersect any nearby aquifers. Tunnel excavation for the UOMDP takes place entirely within the Sri Lankan Highland

Fig. 9 Ingress timing and LOS displacement from the pixel containing the greatest measured subsidence.

Complex (Fig. 10), which is composed primarily of highly fractured pre-Cambrian gneisses³⁴ with demonstrated potential for hosting large volume water ingress events.^{3,4} Surface water resources were significantly impacted around the time peak inflow discharge was reached. This indicates that the bedrock fracture network at depth is interconnected with fractures closer to the surface, allowing for access to both deep and shallow aquifers that are known to exist within the local groundwater regime.^{1,4} This created a situation where overlying strata acted

Fig. 10 Digitized bedrock geology of the study area modified from Cooray, 1982.³⁵

Fig. 11 Volume loss measured from interpolated surfaces using StaMPS and 4-D filtered time series.

as an unconfined aquifer, which then fed through conductive fractures into the tunnel excavation with a head of greater than 200 m.

Predicting water ingress in fractured crystalline rocks presents a difficult task due to the fact that the permeability distribution within fractured crystalline rock is strongly heterogeneous and can range orders of magnitude.³³ This is evidenced by the change in fracture orientation from primarily horizontal to primarily vertical just before the initial onset of water ingress.⁴ This indicates that groundwater storage geometry controls the extent of surface settlement, rather than the tunnel location. In most cases, subsurface fluid storage systems including oil, gas, magma, or water reservoirs are controlled by the host rock structure.²⁹ We suggest that the extent of the NNW–SSE elongated subsidence pattern is likely to be controlled by buried faults that align with previously mapped structural trends in the area.³⁶

Fracture orientation also plays a major role in controlling the magnitude of observed subsidence. In general, subsidence is relatively insensitive to the closure of vertical discontinuities, because their closure allows for intact rock extension in the horizontal direction, which only generates vertical subsidence through a “Poisson’s ratio” effect.³² The closure of horizontal joints, however, contributes directly to vertical shortening. Previous discrete element numerical modeling results show that varying the normal stiffness of horizontal fractures can produce settlements an order of magnitude greater than vertical fractures.⁹ Knowing that conductive fractures are primarily vertical in the region where water ingress was encountered, this may explain how a total water volume loss of 9.2 million m³ can produce much smaller surface volume losses. In this case, estimated surface losses of ~250,000 m³ (Fig. 11) are ~3% of the total water volume loss.

4.3 4-D Filtering Noise Reduction

Implementation of the 4-D filtering technique clearly demonstrates an ability to reduce noise within the dataset. Improvements in the precision of deformation measurements are attained by averaging neighbors in both spatial and temporal domains while allowing different neighbor combinations to be used within the time series. Averaging in the spatial domain is useful when the spatial extent of deformation is much larger than the radius used for averaging; in other words, deformation anomalies at scales that are small relative to the filter radius will

be undetectable after the filter has been applied. Also, the approach used effectively assumes the deformation within the radius to be symmetrical. In our case, the subsidence trough is observed to deepen at a greater rate closer to the center (Fig. 8), which may incorrectly decrease pixel values near the trough during spatial filtering. The inclusion of temporal filtering results in a greater ability to resolve smaller deformations and more easily recognize the onset and gradual increase of subsidence, especially for scenes containing higher levels of noise after PS processing (Fig. 11). This noise is most likely due to turbulent atmosphere, which can cause either a phase increase or decrease depending upon the degree of atmospheric delay present in the master scene relative to that of the slave scenes. It is, therefore, necessary to select a master scene with an average degree of atmospheric delay for time series processing such that atmospheric errors in the results do not strongly correlate through time. The majority of noise reduction occurs within the first few temporal window sizes with diminishing returns thereafter.

When choosing whether to apply a temporal filter, one must take into account the rate of deformation and the temporal resolution of the data. InSAR acquisition rates, limited by the repeat cycle of the satellite constellation, must be high compared to the rate of deformation. This requires a temporal resolution such that the amount of deformation between scene acquisitions is less than the detection limit of the sensor. Satellite InSAR detection limits vary based on surface scattering properties but are usually on the order of several millimeters for C-band sensors.¹⁶ Assuming a detection limit of 3 mm, average deformation rates should not exceed 0.125 mm/day during the time period in which our temporal resolution is 24 days (October 8, 2016, to February 5, 2017) and should not exceed 0.25 mm/day when acquisitions are made every 12 days (after February 5, 2017). An overall average rate of 0.1 mm/day and a maximum sustained rate of 0.15 mm/day are therefore within our limits for observable deformations. If deformation rates exceed detection limits, the application of a temporal filter may create the appearance of artificially reduced deformation rates.

5 Conclusion

Satellite InSAR analysis revealed the development of a ~ 15 km² patch of subsidence near water ingress locations along the headrace tunnel of the UOMDP between October 1, 2016, and November 20, 2017. StaMPS software was used to identify a dense set of over 3500 PS pixels within the highly vegetated area at the surface above the tunnel alignment. A 4-D filtering method applied to the unwrapped PS pixels significantly reduced noise from sources that appear randomly in space and time, increasing our ability to accurately identify the onset of subsidence and measure surface volume loss over time. A maximum average subsidence rate of 0.15 mm/day coincides with maximum water discharge measurements from the tunnel, which indicates that the primary consolidation mechanism is a result of pressure reduction following groundwater drainage and subsequent closure of larger conductive fractures. The observed subsidence bowl is punctuated by localized maxima and extends in an NW–SE orientation, suggesting that the extent of subsidence is governed by previously mapped structural trends of similar orientation. These results highlight the potential for the use of InSAR as a monitoring tool to determine the onset and potential extent of surface subsidence to quickly identify areas at risk of experiencing settlements.

The applied 4-D filtering method is ideal for relatively slow, constant surface deformation. Ultimately, the wavelength of the sensor and the temporal resolution of the dataset determine the maximum deformation rates for which the 4-D filtering technique can be applied. Acquisition rates can be well constrained when using ground-based or airborne SAR methods, however, satellite InSAR systems are limited by their polar orbit repeat cycles. This makes data from relatively low repeat time satellite constellations, such as Sentinel-1, COSMO-SkyMed, and the future RADARSAT Constellation Mission potentially favorable options for 4-D filtering.

Acknowledgments

We thank the two anonymous reviewers for their thorough comments that helped improve this manuscript. This work was supported by the University Transportation Center for Underground

Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI) at the Colorado School of Mines for funding this research under Grant No. 69A3551747118 from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT). The opinions expressed in this paper are those of the authors and not the DOT. The digital geologic map of Sri Lanka was prepared by Aaron Engers, Julia Payne, Jarred Dull, and Bias Adibrata at the Colorado School of Mines.

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